

Termites: the big ecosystem catalysts

Author: José Augusto Roxinol

Main question:

Why termites and ants presence contributes to plants vegetative yield?

Main hypothesis:

Termites accelerate the rates of decomposition and mineralization of Soil Organic Matter done by microorganisms. This would increase the availability of nutrients in the soil, which contributes to an increase in the plant vegetative yield. The ants control the herbivory action, which saves resources of plant defenses that should be destined to their vegetative yield.

Three main references:

- Wilson, Edward O. "The Little Things That Run the world * (The Importance and Conservation of Invertebrates)." *Conservation biology* 1.4 (1987): 344-346. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.1987.tb00055.x>
- Evans, Theodore A., et al. "Ants and termites increase crop yield in a dry climate." *Nature communications* 2 (2011): 262. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms1257>
- Parr, C. L., et al. "Suppression of savanna ants alters invertebrate composition and influences key ecosystem processes." *Ecology* 97.6 (2016): 1611-1617. <https://doi.org/10.1890/15-1713.1>

Perspectives that this project could open for new scientific and/or technological advances?

We will address the neglected issue that termites and ants are crucial agents for the functioning of ecosystems. For this we quantify the role of termites and soil microorganisms, potentially revealing a catalytic effect of these insects on the action of the microbiota. We will also measure a possible conflicting demand on plant growth generated by the positive and negative effects of predation by ants. These effects arise from termite predation (which should positively impact plant growth) and herbivory (which should negatively impact plant growth).

The experimental strategy to be adopted to obtain the answer to the problem and the theoretical-methodological approach to be used:

To measure the positive effect of termites, ants and soil microbiota on plants vegetative yield, we will carry out a long-term and large-scale experiment on a 400 ha fragment of Atlantic Forest. This fragment is located in a forest reserve managed by the Federal University of Viçosa, Minas Gerais, Brazil. With the possibility of expanding the project to another area 2000 km west of Viçosa, in an area of Amazon Forest in Tangará da Serra, Mato Grosso, Brazil. The basic configuration of the experiment consists of four large experimental plots (80 x 80 m each) composing a complete factorial of the presence and absence of termites and ants, totaling 10.2 ha. The exclusion of termites and ants will be done using taxa-specific exclusion techniques adapted from the methods of pest control used in the control of invasive species in urban areas. Such techniques have already been used in wild environments in previous research, showing that they are accurate enough to avoid changes in fauna beyond that already predicted by our hypothesis.

MEASURES: we will evaluate and compare between treatments, variables related to (i) soil, (ii) plants, (iii) soil microbiota and (iv) invertebrate fauna. Specifically, let's assess:

In (i) the physical-chemical characteristics of the soil = water retention, moisture, particle size, water infiltration rate, soil nutrients content (C, N, P, S, K) and volume of termite and ant tunnels.

In (ii) vegetative growth rate, the nutritional content of tissues and rate of herbivory.

In (iii) decomposition rate of Soil Organic Matter; richness, biomass and soil microbiota activity; and the rate of CO₂ produced.

In (iv) density measurements of the invertebrate trophic chain (including at least termites, ants, herbivorous insects, and spiders).

Statistical analysis: The statistical significance will be investigated by Generalized Linear Model (GLM) for each error distribution, investigated the effect of the presence and absence of termites and ants (each "treatment" is one of the four instances of the complete factorial) . The physical and chemical variables of the soil, as well as the variables that describe the activities of the microorganisms, will enter the model as co-variables when appropriate. The choice of the specific set of covariates to be included in a given model will depend on the logic of the hypothesis with which it will be constructed previously and adjusted with the analysis.

Specifics objectives:

- Evaluate the rate of decomposition of the Soil Organic Matter, collecting and measuring the change in the biomass of the litter and wood previously placed in the soil in mesh bags.
- To evaluate the physical and chemical characteristics of the soil and the richness, biomass and microbial activity of the forest soil.
- Evaluate the growth and production of flowers and seeds of plants chosen as models for the experimental effects.
- Evaluate the rate of herbivory in these plants.
- Monitor the fauna of invertebrates.